

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The attitude of people towards the role of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in post-boko haram insurgency in north-eastern part of Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was designed to evaluate the attitude of people towards the role of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in post-boko haram insurgency in north-eastern part of Nigeria. The researcher uses descriptive design of a survey type to collect relevant information. The sample size for the study was 359 participants comprising 25 staff of states ministry of health, and 334 respondents from IDPs and general public. The researcher stratified random sampling technique was used to draw the sample needed for the study in three geopolitical Zones in the States, (Zone A, B and C). Structured questionnaire was the major instruments used collect data for analysis. Result presented in tables analyses the perception of people on the role of saves the children program of WHO in the north east, item 1 state that provision of food and shelter helps in reviving the children, this state was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 2 also state that, in post-boko haram insurgency food provision was accessible to everyone illegible individual this statement was also accepted with 3.76 and 1.48 mean and standard deviation respectively. Similarly, item 3 state that, the food aid saved the life of many and avoided starvation in the affected areas, the statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 4 also state that food provision of food is not the best way to revive the victims, this statement was vehemently rejected with a mean and standard deviation of 2.56 and 1.87 respectively. item 5 on the other hand discusses provision of well-balanced diet given to the vulnerable so that they will not be malnourished, this statement was accepted by the respondent with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively.

Keywords: Attitudes; Perception; People; Non-governmental organization; Insurgency

1. Background

The continued increase in the spread of the nefarious activities of the Boko Haram sect in North East Nigeria since 2009 has created adverse humanitarian consequence to the North East region. Life in the various communities of Borno, Yobe and Adamawa states, such as Kawuri, Baga, Konduga, Bama, Shuwa, Ajigin, Gamboru, Giwa, Chibok, Gwoza to mention a few, have been characteristically nasty, brutish and most times short (Salkida, 2012). The region has ceased to know civil normalcy as a result in the dire humanitarian situation as evident in human casualties, human right abuses, population displacement, and refugee debacle, loss of means of livelihood, food insecurity, limited medical facilities and other social amenities. The increasing influx of refugees and the spillover of Boko Haram violence to neighboring countries over the years had resulted to serious regional security implications, despite the establishment of a Joint Border Patrol Command to address the increasing security challenges attributed to the insurgency. Normalcy has gradually coming to stay and the efforts of NGOs can never be underestimated. However, different unproven

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information is emanating on the roles of the NGOs in the area. The study therefore will assess the attitude and perception of people in the north-eastern state towards the role of NGOs in Post-Boko Haram Insurgency.

2. Introduction

The recent crises across the globe is a proof that insurgency has become a threat to global peace and security throughout the 21st century. Insurgency resurfaced and become the highest contributor to humanitarian crises in the form of rise in human casualties, internally displaced persons, refugee debacles, food insecurity and the spread of various diseases (Joda & Abdulrasheed 2015). The ultimate goal of save the children program was to restore a better future for the affected children who might have lost their parents or have become traumatized due to the insurgency crises, even the young children who happen to be part of the Boko-haram team deserve to be saved and be given better education for the benefits of their future and the good and smooth running of Nigeria. Education is the key to brightening the life of children as UNICEF (2016) reported that 7 million Nigerians majority of which are children, have been internally displaced and exposed to frequent Boko haram attack, which has implications for their education career, mental health, and their general well-being, the children are rarely assessed and provided with poor feeding, poor access to social amenities. Forced school closure and vandalization of school facilities have led many school children out of the education system in general. (Isokpan, 2016). Stated that in Maiduguri which shares a border with Yobe and Adamawa States, life is full of insecurity; fear has become part of the people in the affected states as many of the children are either affected by phobia or trauma. Everybody is asking which area is going to be attacked next. Is it his/her area? Boko Haram activities have greatly affected amenities like schools, houses, hospitals, markets, electricity, and etcetera. Secondary schools in Borno State, for instance, have greatly been affected; almost all the secondary schools in areas affected by the insurgent attacks have been closed down and have affected the school facilities, students' enrollments, attendance, teachers absconding and teachers' job performance. (Isokpan, 2016). Further commented that the state government has attempted to re-locate the affected schools in the affected areas to State capitals, but facilities to accommodate the large number of students are inadequate as some of the existing schools in the State capital have been converted to camps for internally displaced persons. (Isokpan, 2016). Observed after close discussion with students and teachers affected by the insurgents the devastation impact of the activities of Boko Haram had on them ranging from destruction of school facilities, forced school closure and loss of teachers and students' lives which also affected teachers' job performance in the affected states. Waldek and Jayasekara, (2011) stated that Boko Haram is the mixture of two words. A Hausa Language word Boko and another Arabic Language word Haram. Boko refers to 'book' or, the noun, ilimin that means 'education', while Haram means forbidden. The word Boko was principally used derogatively in reference to the colonial-style education, as opposed to ilimin Islamiyya (Islamic Education). Basically, Boko Haram is widely used to translate as 'Western Education' is forbidden, a sin or sacrilege Abdullahi (2017) opined that however, the leader of the sect as of August 2009, Mallam Sani Umaru discard such designation. According to him, Boko Haram does not actually meant that as people Ilorin Journal of Administration and Development, University of Ilorin Vol 3 (1), June 2017 3 widely regard the sect and as the infidel media continue to portray. He advanced that Boko Haram doesn't mean 'Western Education is a sin', rather 'Western Civilisation is forbidden'. The sect is an Islamic group that is in operation in northern Nigeria and came to prominence in 2009. Mohammed Yusuf, a fiery leader and resident of Maiduguri, founded it. Initially, the group was not violent until the introduction of bike-helmet law in 2009 by the then President Umaru Musa Yar'adua which saw the stiff resistance by the members of the sect. Later, several clashes between the armed forces and members of the sect were recorded on several occasions. Mustapha (2015) noted that Boko Haram later went underground and reorganised themselves, change their tactics of operation after the demise of Mohammed Yusuf and today under the leadership of Abubakar Shekau. Since 2010, they have used Improvised Explosive Devices, kidnappings, driveby shootings, targeted assassination and suicide bombings (Abdullahi, 2017).

Oyawale, A. (2018) Wrote that Boko Haram is a violent takfiri jihadist movement operating mostly in northeastern Nigeria but whose operational reach extends into the neighboring countries of Niger, Chad, and Cameroon. Takfir, which will be discussed in more detail below, is an Islamic concept translating as excommunication, or the declaring of a nominal Muslim as an apostate. The interpretation and implementation of this concept in practice has been a constant dividing line between the various factions that are known as "Boko Haram". Oyawale, A. (2018) Stated that the name "Boko Haram" itself is often translated as "Western education is blasphemous". While this encapsulates one element of the group's ideology (its stance against Western education and any teachings that are not strictly based on the Qur'an), it is a name that the movement has consistently rejected but that the media and politicians have embraced as what is, in essence, a slur against the movement.

Abubakar Aballahhi (2012) viewed the name constricts our understanding of what Boko Haram is by endorsing a monolithic view of Boko Haram as anti-education when, in fact, the movement has and continues to be divided into factions that represent doctrines beyond education. As early as Boko Haram's formation in August 2009 as a self-avowed jihadist group, Abubakar Shekau the then new leader, said "Western education is part of a broader civilizational

project to detach Muslims from Islam and its Arabic language traditions, and instead immerse Muslims in Christianity and English-language". Thus, opposition to Western education is but one ingredient in a much broader construction of Boko Haram ideology. Since 2009, Boko Haram leaders officially called the movement Jamaat Ahl asSunnah Lid dawa wa al-Jihad (Sunni Group for Proselytization and Jihad), or JAS, and published statements to reaffirm that they are – at least in their mindset – the “pure” Ahl alSunna. Oyawale, A. (2018) mentioned that those who did not join JAS, including “mainstream” Muslims, and Salafists who “sold out” to the Nigerian state, are not part of Ahl al-Sunna, instead classified as kafir or infidels. Not all factions of Boko Haram, however, follow this line of thinking which is key to Shekau’s JAS faction.

2.1. Statement of the Problem

The need for the protection of children in Northern Nigeria in post-Boko haram insurgency is critical given the fact that that only about 10 per cent of the Boko Haram victims are accommodated by formal camps maintained by national and international humanitarian organizations that are based mostly in urban areas (Ibrahim et al. 2017). This has prompted different governmental and non-governmental organizations to come to the aid of victims. A world health organization program (Save the children) has laid down its focus on the children, their attempt to provide food, shelter, accommodation and education to the affected children has gone a long way in helping many children get out of traumatic conditions caused by the insurgency. However, this has also created different types of criticism in respect to their role in northern Nigeria, many are raising concern on the objectives of the organization and the manner through which they carry out their duties and concern on rape, robbery, corruption and different forms of irregularities were some issues raised to question the role of the organization in the State. This has led to a serious concern in the mind of the general public and the state ministry of health who seek to find out where these NGOs has gone out of normal in the way they deliver their services. Hence this study wishes to assess the people’s attitude and attitudes the WHO save the children programme in the post-boko haram insurgency era in the north-east.

2.1.1. Research Questions

- What is the attitude of the people of North easth, Nigeria on child health care provision offered by NGOs in Post-Boko haram insurgency?
- What is the attitude of the people of North easth, Nigeria provision of education to children by WHO (save the children) after Post-Boko Haram insurgency?
- What is the attitude of the people of North easth, Nigeria child protection offered by WHO (save the children) after Post-Boko Haram insurgency?
- What is the attitude of the people of North easth, Nigeria food intervention provided by WHO (save the children) after post the Boko haram insurgency?
- What is the attitude of the people of North easth, Nigeria provision of livelihood by WHO (save the children) after post boko haram insurgency?

2.1.2. Research Design

The design of this study is the descriptive design of a survey type. A survey research design according to Saris & Gallhofer, (2014) is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group of population. This design was considered appropriate and suitable for this study because it focuses on obtaining information and analyzing data from a group of staff from ministry of health and Boko haram victims from IDPs and the general public considered to be representative of the entire population about their attitude and attitude towards the role of who (save the children program) in Post-Boko Haram insurgency era in Yobe State, Nigeria.

2.1.3. Population of the Study

The entire population states are put at 9.4million people based on the 2006 population census. The target population of this study is the inhabitants’ three local government areas that were purposively selected for detailed analysis. The population for this study is thus 433672 while the unit of analysis consists of staff of primary health care, Refugees from IDPs and the general community from the selected three local governments from each state.

2.2. Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size for the study was 359 participants comprising 25 staff of states ministry of health, and 334 respondents from IDPs and general public. The researcher used stratified random sampling technique to draw the sample needed for the study in three geopolitical Zones in the States, (Zone A, B and C). The three geopolitical Zones in the study area

will be used as strata. Hence, simple random sampling by lucky dip will be employed to select the participants. Taherdoost, (2016) stated that sampling is very necessary when there is an infinitely large number to be managed within the time and financial constraint.

2.2.1. Research Instrument

Structured questionnaire was the major instruments to collect data for this study. The researcher designed the questionnaire titled “Assessment of Attitude of People towards the Role of NGOs in Post-Boko Haram Insurgency in the north-east, Nigeria”. The questionnaire is made of three section section A, B, and C, section A will consist of the profile of the respondent, this include name, age, gender, and qualification, section B comprised of question questions particularly on the perception of people of Yobe state on the role of save the children program in post boko haram insurgency in Yobe state. Similarly section C involved question on the attitude of the people towards the program. For the respondents to respond to four (4) point likert type rating scales of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), and Strongly Disagreed (SD) respectively. The items in the questionnaire were structured based on stated research questions.

2.2.2. Validation of Research Instrument

The instrument to be used to collect data for this study will be validated by three senior lecturers and above in the department of physical and health education, Bayero University, Kano. The corrections and suggestions made will be strictly adhered to before producing the final copy of the instrument.

3. Method of Data Collection

A letter of introduction was collected from the head of department, department of physical and health education University Maiduguri, which was taken to the ministry of health and to the director IDPs camp in the selected areas of the states. After securing the permission from the designated authorities the questionnaire will then be distributed to the selected respondents in the geopolitical zones of the state (Zone A, Zone B and Zone C) The researcher will be assisted by four research assistants who are the staff of state ministry of health. After respondents filled the questionnaire, the researcher will then collect the filled questionnaire on-the-spot.

3.1. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected for this study will be analyzed using mean and standard deviation as statistical tools. A four (4) of points rating scale of likert’s types will be used with assigned values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 as options to the items on the questionnaires. These options are:-

Strongly Agreed (SA) - 4points

Agreed (A) - 3points

Disagreed (D) - 2points

Strongly Disagreed (SD) - 1point

The mean of the above is determined by calculating the average.

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum fx}{n}$$

Where,

\bar{X} = mean

F= frequency

X= nominal value of option

\sum = summation sign

N= number of the respondent

A cut- off point of 2.50 was used to determine the mean which is thus:

$$\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50$$

This means that any mean score equal to or greater than was considered as agreed response and any mean score less than (<) 2.50 was considered as disagreed responses.

4. Results and discussion

The table below analysis the perception of people on the role of saves the children program of WHO in the north east, item 1 state that provision of food and shelter helps in reviving the children, this state was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 2 also state that, in post-boko haram insurgency food provision was accessible to everyone illegible individual this statement was also accepted with 3.76 and 1.48 mean and standard deviation respectively. Similarly, item 3 state that, the food aid saved the life of many and avoided starvation in the affected areas, the statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 4 also state that food provision of food is not the best way to revive the victims, this statement was vehemently rejected with a mean and standard deviation of 2.56 and 1.87 respectively. item 5 on the other hand discusses provision of well-balanced diet given to the vulnerable so that they will not be malnourished, this statement was accepted by the respondent with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively.

Table 1 The attitude of the people of North east, Nigeria food intervention provided by WHO (save the children) after post the Boko haram insurgency

S/N	Statement Strategy	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	Provision of food and shelter helps in reviving the children	3.56	1.46	Accept
2	Food provision was accessible to everyone illegible	3.76	1.48	Accept
3	The food aid saved the life of many and avoided starvation	3.56	1.46	Accept
4	Provision of food is not the best way to revive the victims	2.56	1.87	Reject
5	Well balanced diet is given to them so that they will not be malnourished.	3.56	1.46	Accept

Source: Field work 2022

Table 2 The attitude of the people of North-east, Nigeria provision of education to children by WHO (save the children) after Post-Boko Haram insurgency

S/N	Statement Strategy	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	Access to education is the key item given in post-insurgency	2.45	1.89	Reject
2	Save the children provided the ways for children to return to classroom	3.56	1.46	Accept
3	Renovation of schools and free education program was helpful	3.76	1.48	Accept
4	Monitoring and examplinary leadership was helpful	2.45	1.89	Reject

Source: Field work 2022

The table above discusses the perception of people on the aspect of education. Item 1 state access to education is the key item given in post-insurgency; this statement was rejected by the majority of the respondent with a mean and standard deviation of 2.45 and 1.89 respectively. Item 2 also state that save the children program provided the ways for children to return to classroom, this statement was rejected with a mean and standard deviation of 2.45 and 1.88 respectively. Item 3 also state that renovation of schools and free education program by the WHO sector was helpful, this statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.76 and 1.48 respectively. Item 4 state that monitoring and examplinary leadership program was helpful, this statement was rejected with a mean and standard of 2.45 and 1.89 respectively.

The table below provided the perception of people in the area on the role of WHO in terms of child protection. Item 1 state that, the child protection program is fake and political, this statement was rejected with a mean and standard

deviation of 2.34 and 1.89 respectively. Item 2 on the other hand state that, the child protection program is helpful and helps many children rediscover their purpose. This statement was accepted with a mean and standard of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 3 also state that many children were saved as a result of the program, the statement was rejected with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 4 also state that the program makes many children reluctant and weak. This statement was however rejected with a mean and standard deviation of 3.76 and 1.48 respectively.

Table 3 The attitude of the people of North-east, Nigeria child protection offered by WHO (save the children) in Post-Boko Haram insurgency

S/N	Statement Strategy	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	The child protection program is fake and political	2.34	1.89	Reject
2	The child protection program is helpful and helps many children rediscover their purpose.	3.56	1.46	Accept
3	Many children were saved as a result of the program	3.56	1.46	Accept
4	The program makes many children reluctant and weak	3.76	1.48	Accept

Source: Field work 2022

Table 4 The attitude of the people of North east, Nigeria on child health care provision offered by NGOs in Post-Boko haram insurgency

S/N	Statement Strategy	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	They contribute to peace-building activities aimed at ensuring good relations	3.55	1.47	Accept
2	The civil organizations assisted the victims to obtain a legal remedy, including compensation and adequate health care.	3.55	1.47	Accept
3	Civil society organizations (CSOs) also played the role of monitoring situations of forcible displacement in the state	2.45	1.87	Reject
4	Efforts to provide adequate protection and assistance to internally displaced	3.56	1.46	Accept
5	Adequate medical care was given to victims and the vulnerable especially to their pregnant, nursing mothers and children	3.56	1.46	Accept

Source: Field work 2022

The table above discusses the perception of people on provision of health care by the NGOs. Item 1 state that they contribute to peace-building activities aimed at ensuring good relations and good health, this statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.55 and 1.47 respectively. Item 2 also state that the civil organizations assisted the victims to obtain a legal remedy, including compensation and adequate health care, this statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.55 and 1.47 respectively. Item 3 state that the civil society organizations (CSOs) also played the role of monitoring situations of forcible displacement in the state, this statement was rejected with a mean and standard deviation of 2.45 and 1.87 respectively. Item 4 state that an effort to provide adequate protection and assistance to internally displace, this statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 5 state that adequate medical care was given to victims and the vulnerable especially to their pregnant, nursing mothers and children, this statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively.

The table below discusses the aspect of livelihood given by the NGOs. Item 1 state that Skills and the creation of livelihood opportunities to enable them to start rebuilding their lives, this statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.54 and 1.46 respectively. Item 2 state that the NGs prevent overt conditions on their territory that might compel population to flee; this statement was also accepted with a mean of 3.56 and standard deviation of 1.46 respectively. Item 3 state that vocational training and skill acquisition helped the victims so that they don't stay idle while, this statement was accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.56 and 1.46 respectively. Item 4 state that the NGOs Played a role of providing funding from the Commonwealth of Nations and gifts to countries, this statement was also accepted with a mean and standard deviation of 3.76 and 1.48 respectively.

Table 5 What is the attitude of the people of North-east, Nigeria provision of livelihood by WHO (save the children) in post-boko haram insurgency

S/N	Statement Strategy	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1	Skills and the creation of livelihood opportunities, to enable them to start rebuilding their lives.	3.54	1.46	Accept
2	Prevent overt conditions on their territory that might compel population to flee.	3.56	1.46	Accept
3	Vocational training and skill acquisition so that they don't stay idle while.	3.56	1.46	Accept
4	Played a role of providing funding from the Commonwealth of Nations and gifts to countries	3.76	1.48	Accept

Source: Field work 2022

5. Conclusion

The study was designed to evaluate the attitude of people towards the role of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in post-boko haram insurgency in north-eastern part of Nigeria. The result shows that with the efforts of NGOs Educational output (human capital investments) is influenced by Boko Haram insurgency hence measures were taken to caution the effects of the menace. It is concluded that the level of investment in human being required to be achieved a given educational level will not be attained with the of Boko Haram insurgency, this is because, Boko Haram insurgency resulted to a high level of student's dropout. Improving the level of school enrolment: school's attendance and school infrastructure significantly determine the level of educational output. That is, the higher the level of school enrolment, school attendance and school's infrastructure, the higher the level of educational output. This implies that educational output will increase with the increase in the level of school enrolment, school attendance and school's infrastructure.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest in the work, however, traces of constructive criticism was observed at the cost of data collection but eventually, mutual agreement was made at end and result submitted is a product of duly accepted process by all members of the team.

Statement of ethical approval

All protocols involving ethical standard has been followed duly. Permission for data collection and approval for risks instances were strictly taken into consideration before any practical work was observed. Experience laboratory attendant were made available and strict were followed accordingly.

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